

ONLINE DATA SUPPLEMENT

Impact of COVID-19 on exercise pathophysiology. A combined cardiopulmonary and echocardiographic exercise study.

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e-Table 1. Respiratory mechanics of the study population at rest and at peak exercise

	Control patients N=18	COVID-19 patients N=18	p-value
REST			
IC, L	3.0 (1.0)	1.7 (0.8)	<0.001
EELV, L	0.97 (0.62)	0.79 (0.54)	0.809
EELV, %FVC	22 (12)	34 (18)	0.064
V_T, L	0.63 (0.42)	0.54 (0.13)	0.097
V_T, %FVC	20 (14)	21 (15)	0.754
EILV, L	1.97 (1.25)	1.06 (1.00)	0.002
EILV, %FVC	59 (15)	42 (23)	0.066
PEAK EXERCISE			
IC, L	2.8 (1.2)	1.7 (0.8)	0.002
EELV, L	1.04 (0.67)	0.83 (0.60)	0.096
EELV %FVC	27 (12)	28 (16)	0.525
V_T, L	1.85 (0.93)	1.14 (0.42)	0.004
V_T, %FVC	50 (14)	45 (22)	0.880
EILV, L	0.76 (0.47)	0.58 (0.72)	0.153
EILV%FVC	21 (13)	26 (25)	0.997

Abbreviations: EELV=end-expiratory lung volume, EILV=end-inspiratory lung volume, FVC= forced vital capacity, IC=inspiratory capacity, V_T=tidal volume.

e-Table 2. General characteristics of study population, subdivided according to the type of ventilatory support required during hospitalization (mechanical ventilation, non-invasive ventilation, oxygen).

	MV N=5	NIV N=9	O ₂ N=4	p-value
Demographics and anthropometrics				
Age, years	54.3 (10.9)**	72.8 (14.5)	52.8 (19.8)	0.008
BMI, Kg/m ²	25.5 (1.6)	26.5 (3.2)	25.2 (2.0)	0.8
Hospitalization				
Hospitalization length, days	38.0 (13.0) ^o	30.0 (5.0) [§]	10.5 (13.8)	0.01
Length of ventilator or O ₂ support, days	35.0 (5.0)* ^o	22.0 (9.0) [§]	2.0 (0.5)	0.003
Blood tests				
Hemoglobin, g/dL	11.8 (1.4)	11.1 (2.1)	12.0 (3.7)	0.6
Creatinine, mg/dL	0.8 (0.1)	0.9 (0.2)	0.7 (0.2)	0.1
C-reactive protein, mg/dL	0.1 (0.9)	0.3 (0.3)	1.0 (4.8)	0.6
BNP, pg/mL	21 (15)	69 (88)	37 (59)	0.2
Pulmonary function test				
FVC, L	2.05 (1.3)	2.65 (0.98)	3.83 (0.88)	0.4
FVC, % predicted	41.7 (23.47)	86.65 (49.12)	92.51 (23.28)	0.06
FEV ₁ , L/min	2.01 (1.11)	1.74 (0.81)	2.895 (1.47)	0.6
FEV ₁ , % predicted	50.38 (24.59)	100.3 (48.26)	95.15 (10.28)	0.08
FEV ₁ /FVC	84.84 (16.09)	83.33 (12.27)	82.08 (7.182)	0.5
Echocardiography				
LV EF, %	0.55 (0.06)	0.59 (0.05)	0.54 (0.08)	0.6
LV mass index, g/m ²	86.4 (20.5)	88.2 (26.9)	82.5 (6.5)	0.7
RV diameter, mm	40.0 (7.0)	43.0 (6.0)	36.0 (6.5)	0.5
Septal E/E'	7.6 (2.3)	13.4 (7.7)	8.8 (4.8)	0.08
LA volume, mL	58 (21)	59 (35.5)	53 (12.5)	>0.9
S' wave, cm/s	0.12 (0.04)	0.14 (0.01)	0.12 (0.03)	0.2
Hemodynamics, oxygen delivery and extraction at rest				
SBP, mmHg	125 (13)	140 (5)	120 (10)	0.2
SPAP, mmHg	24.2 (5.2)	29.8 (5.7) [§]	22.6 (1.3)	0.008
S' RV /SPAP, cm/s/mmHg	0.47 (0.08)	0.47 (0.17)	0.54 (0.08)	0.2
HR, bpm	93 (10)*	75 (21)	79 (8.75)	0.022
CO, L/min	6.9 (1.6)	4.6 (1.4)	4.6 (1.8)	0.06
SaO ₂ , %	98.2 (1.5)	97.5 (1.3)	98.9 (0.3)	0.08
CaO ₂ , mL/dL	17.5 (3.6)	17.1 (5.1)	15.8 (5.3)	0.8
CvO ₂ , mL/dL	11.4 (4.0)	9.8 (3.4)	10.1 (7.8)	>0.9
C(a-v)O ₂ mL/dL	5.8 (2.3)	5.6 (2.0)	5.5 (2.3)	>0.9
C(a-v)O ₂ / CaO ₂	0.39 (0.12)	0.33 (0.13)	0.37 (0.27)	>0.9

Abbreviations: BMI=body mass index, BNP=brain natriuretic peptide, CaO₂= content of oxygen in arterial blood, C(a-v)O₂=arteriovenous oxygen difference, CO=cardiac output, EF=ejection fraction, FVC= forced

vital capacity, FEV₁= forced expiratory volume in one second, HR=heart rate, LA=left atrium, LV=left ventricle, MV=mechanical ventilation, NIV=non-invasive ventilation, O₂=oxygen, RV=right ventricle, SaO₂= arterial oxygen saturation, SBP=systolic blood pressure, SPAP=systolic pulmonary artery pressure.

*p<0.05 MV vs NIV, ** p<0.01 MV vs NIV, °p<0.05 MV vs O₂, §p<0.05 NIV vs O₂.

e-Table 2. Ventilatory and hemodynamic parameters of study population at peak exercise, subdivided according to the type of ventilatory support required during hospitalization (mechanical ventilation, non-invasive ventilation, oxygen).

	MV N=5	NIV N=9	O₂ N=4	p-value
Oxygen transport and gas-exchange				
VO ₂ , mL/Kg/min	12.7 (3.9)	13.8 (4.7)	17.4 (3.6)	0.4
VO ₂ , % of predicted	42.4 (7.4)	76.3 (32.4)	65.3 (23.4)	0.08
SaO ₂ , %	96.9 (1.0)*°	94.0 (2.4) ^{§§}	99.4 (0.6)	0.004
PaO ₂ , mmHg	81 (5)	68 (15) ^{§§}	105 (7.25)	0.008
PaCO ₂ , mmHg	36 (3)	37 (6)	37.5 (5)	0.8
CaO ₂ , mL/dL	18.3 (4.0)	16.7 (5.1)	17.3 (4.9)	0.3
CvO ₂ , mL/dL	6.3 (1.2)	6.3 (3.3)	4.3 (5.0)	0.7
C(a-v)O ₂ mL/dL	11.7 (1.0)	10.5 (3.1)	13.4 (1.2)	0.06
C(a-v)O ₂ / CaO ₂	0.65 (0.05)	0.60 (0.16)	0.76 (0.23)	0.2
RQ	0.99 (0.10)	1.12 (0.21)	1.17 (0.15)	0.4
Lac, mmol/L	2.7 (1.5)	3 (3.3)	4.15 (1.1)	0.3
Ventilatory adaptation				
VE, L/min	43.7 (2.3)	40.6 (17.6)	47.1 (22.7)	0.7
VE/MVV	63.7 (34.9)	58.8 (5.3)	54.4 (17.6)	0.6
RR, /min	35 (4)	34 (11)	36 (13)	0.8
VE/VO ₂	37 (10)	42 (8)	36 (13)	0.6
VE/VCO ₂	42 (7)	40 (6)	34 (10)	0.5
VE/VCO ₂ slope	31 (6)	33 (5)	29 (6)	0.5
PetO ₂ , mmHg	116.4 (5)	118.5 (5.7)	112.7 (6.225)	0.6
PetCO ₂ , mmHg	34.1 (5.6)	32.9 (2.6)	37.3 (5.775)	0.3
V _D /V _T	0.41 (0.12)	0.38 (0.16)	0.30 (0.16)	0.3
Cardiovascular adaptation				
HR, bpm	122 (15)	111 (44)	120 (25.5)	0.8
CO, L/min	11.3 (1.1)	9.8 (3.5)	8.3 (3.8)	0.3
SBP, mmHg	150 (20)	180 (20)	160 (52.5)	0.8
SPAP, mmHg	43.6 (3.8)	54.0 (7.9) [§]	44.7 (3.8)	0.02
TPR, WU	2.7 (0.9)	3.7 (1.1)	4.5 (1.0)	0.1
S' RV, cm/s	0.22 (0.0675)	0.185 (0.05)	0.16 (0.045)	0.2
S' RV /SPAP, cm/s/mmHg	0.48 (0.08)	0.35 (0.06)	0.30 (0.10)	0.2

Abbreviations: CaO₂= content of oxygen in arterial blood, C(a-v)O₂=arteriovenous oxygen difference, CO=cardiac output, HR=heart rate, MV=mechanical ventilation, MVV=maximal voluntary ventilation, NIV=non-invasive ventilation, O₂=oxygen, PetO₂=end-tidal pressure for oxygen, PetCO₂= end-tidal pressure for carbon dioxide, RQ=respiratory quotient, RR=respiratory rate, RV=right ventricle, SaO₂= arterial oxygen saturation, SBP=systolic blood pressure, SPAP=systolic pulmonary artery pressure, TPR=total pulmonary vascular resistance, VE=minute ventilation, VCO₂=carbon dioxide production, VO₂= oxygen consumption.

*p<0.05 MV vs NIV, °p<0.05 MV vs O₂, §p<0.05 NIV vs O₂, §§p<0.01 NIV vs O₂.

e-Figure legend

e-Figure 1. Oxygen consumption at peak exercise as a function of hemoglobin content

Abbreviations: Hb=hemoglobin; VO₂=oxygen consumption

e-Figure 2. Individual pressure-flow pairs of the pulmonary circulation in COVID-19 patients and in controls

Abbreviations: mPAP=mean pulmonary artery pressure

e-Figure 3. Poon-adjusted pressure-flow relationship of the pulmonary circulation in COVID-19 and control subjects.

Abbreviations: mPAP=mean pulmonary artery pressure